

ALCOHOL AND ITS THREE DIMENSIONAL EFFECTS TO AND THROUGH AN INDIVIDUAL

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Abstract:

This is a material to represent, what alcohol does to an individual and through an individual? Alcoholism in an evil, affects all the departments of one's life. As far as alcoholism is concerned only with individuals, it is a deviant behavior but from the grounds of families, it creates a disease effect and if it is seen through the spectacles of society, it becomes a great sin and finally apart from the above all it happens to be a bane to the whole humanity. Though alcoholism starts and even ends with the individual himself, the extended effects include the whole human community. There are many types of addictions but among all those, visibly nothing is seen so worst than that of alcohol addiction.

Key Words: Alcohol, Alcoholism, Effects & Well Being

Introduction:

The subjective and objective consequences of alcohol that occur to an individual and in his interactions with or in the environment around are all together can be brought under three dimensions, and those three dimensions are action level, thought level and conscious level consequences. Human beings are the supreme creations having the integration of body, mind and soul but many are unaware of it but all have been provided with a privilege to understand and realize the same. According Annie Besant, all the things around are made up of atoms and molecules, they are essentially a living thing, so our body also buildup of innumerable lives and they are always coming and going, and always changing. There is not a moment in our life in which one is not sending out swarms of those lives and receives in other swarms of lives. Particles that go out and of those come in, obviously carry the mint –stamping of the source along with it and leave the imprint on the destination to in which it may enter/allowed in. So the atoms from the body penetrated with alcohol, makes more sensible here. If sober people get atoms in to their bodies, they may suffer in to that fashion. So alcoholism is not a mere self –regarding matter, the drunkards are the poison to the community.

Objectives:

- ✓ Have been prepared with an intention to create awareness somewhat differently, on what serious effects does alcoholism brings to an individual and his wellness.
- ✓ To examine, that 'to what degree does it extend its effects'.

Body, Mind and Soul:

Human beings are the perfect blend of body, mind and soul. If anyone of these faculties reach up or sub normal functioning while under the influence of alcohol, it would be a problem for the person himself and for those around. Alcohol by nature possesses the quality to affect and destroy these three faculties. So people under the influence of alcohol generally suffer poor physic, weak mind and a lifeless soul. But People in control are people whose bodies, minds, and spirits are integrated into a strong, healthy whole. (Monti, PM *et al*).

Three Dimensional Consequences:

It has been found that alcohol plays a causative role in occurrence of more than 60 types of diseases and disabilities. This also impacts one's action, thought and consciousness.

(i) At Action Level- Body as a Means - Impacts Sociologically: Family, friends, relatives, neighbors, co-workers or it can be a co-passenger, all could come under the social fabric group. There are three factors which decides the degree of sufferings by them; they are, primarily the level of his physical ability to fulfill the due responsibilities towards self, family and society; secondly the level of drinking and the related out shown behavior by the particular individual and thirdly the physical proximity experienced by the social group. The negative effects of drinking on non-drinking family members remain a cause of concern and a pertinent public health issue. The Inability of the addict in keeping them with a safe, secured and a healthy life style may let them have a complexity and prevent from being a better part of the society. Transition of such effects will go on to a number of descendents. Alcoholism rates first in the family related issues, such as, family violence, spousal/child abuse, divorce and on the normal functioning of the family. Many studies have shown that unemployment, poor work performance and work place accidents and drinking tend to go together. According to industry association sources from India, 15% to 20% of absenteeism and 40% of accidents at work are due to alcohol consumption. Since alcohol impairs good judgment, it is closely linked with higher rates of violent crime such as murder, theft, sexual abuse, physical clash etc., for all, the social group members fall a prey. Importantly alcohol ingestion is found to be the major reason for majority of road accidents.

(ii) At Thought Level -Mind as its Means- Impacts Psychology: Psychology includes all about one's mind and behavior and agrees with all aspects of conscious and unconscious experiences and exposure. Alcohol is a depressant, alcohol on the brain depresses central nervous system and results in major depressive disorder, but there is a fake reasoning that alcohol acts an aid in managing depression. (*Marlene Oscar-Berman et al.*) Thought and action are closely related. If thoughts carry pain or pleasure they become emotional. Negative Emotions often ends with suicides. Generally Alcoholics emotional quotient is not up to a satisfactory mark, so psychological effects of alcohol also appears to be an increase in suicidal behaviors:

- ✓ People hospitalized for suicide attempts found that alcoholics were 75 times more likely to go on to successfully commit suicide than non-alcoholic suicide attempters.
- ✓ The increased risk of suicide compared to the general public is 5 - 20 times greater for alcoholics. (Sher.L)

Studies have found that there is a meaningful difference between the addicts and non addicts, in their personality factors, personality and self concepts are related to one other. If self concept is not up to the satisfactory level, it triggers the person to value himself low, this ends with exhibiting some psychic behaviors, which may be of morally and ethically questionable. (*Mohamad Khaledian et al.*) Alcohol also closely related with sleeping and eating disorders, over a period of time this ends with physical and psychological problems. Cognitive abilities such as shortened attention span, memory, reasoning, decision making, and problem solving all will get arrested by alcohol and also they experience problems in coordination and co-operation, this will make them isolated and will induce further to experience more of anxiety and depression. If they negatively outbursts to express these emotions, it will create problems for the self and others.

(iii) At Conscious Level - by Concealing the Spirit - Impacts Spirituality: Consciousness is the state of true awareness of any object or something within oneself. It can understandably be called as having a sense of selfhood. Consciousness and

spirituality may spell and sound differently, but they mean the same. Since the point/stage at which the ultimate realization of the consciousness has attained, is the place where the word spirituality is to be answered. Alcoholism never helps in attainment of any higher consciousness, but totally interrupts. Even drinking a little socially, dimmer the light of consciousness and old unconscious patterns will start surfacing. Human beings are naturally spiritual in nature, but alcohol induces a transition from human being to animal. Animals by nature are not so harmful in their own way, but a thinking animal is always destructive. Spirituality feeds the soul. Soul is superior to body and mind. Alcohol clouds the soul off from the natural existence, hence the conscious level diminishes. This directly hits the higher nature of human being, such as values, moral and ethics. A man with absence of good qualities in him will always be ranked below the animals.

Summary:

Man is a social animal; he can't live by himself without the influence/support of society. Every one of us is a part of this big networking system. So each one has to fulfill their responsibility towards self, family and society, in order to live happily and let others live happily. But a devil under name alcoholism destroys everything.

Suggestions:

Being a part of the society, one's deviant behaviour should not interfere with the prerogatives of others in all sorts. For that,

- ✓ First to all, it is government's prime responsibility to protect its civilians from engaging such kind of evils, so, the government should be too responsible, from now it should not aim generating fund out of making the innocents fool.
- ✓ Effective awareness programs to reach out and successful rehabilitation measures to work it out.
- ✓ Preventive measures – youths should be made strongly educated on alcohol and related harm.
- ✓ And finally, all of us can sincerely pray God, to take away through any way, the alcohol out from the minds and from the availability, in order to turn all of them towards seeking him.

Conclusion:

It is made clearer to a certain extent that in no way, the alcohol is responsible for doing a good to an addict. Since the intensity of the effect over the identifiable identities of a man (body, mind and spirit) is almost with the same in severity, it becomes hard for him to distinguish the present with that of real self and it become less possible to let a hand to receive a help through any of those three faculties. Since the spirit itself is clouded by alcohol, so no guide for body and mind. They simply turn to serve the alcohol. This would be the condition of him, until an effort is made to break the barrier. This is the reason, why alcoholism is called as "spiritual bankruptcy?"

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